

Content analysis: qualitative coding framework for most transformative visions with definitions and sources

	Comment or Description from vision (<100 words)
Vision Id and Name (if available)	
Is there enough information in the description/template or should the source(s) be consulted?	
Main Purpose or Goal -> Specify what is the main purpose or goal of the vision.	
The 'What' -> Describe the desirable future for nature and people envisioned, i.e., how the world would be if it is achieved. This information can be explicit or implicit. If you cannot extract it, ask the coder. If he/she cannot extract it, it should be deleted from the database.	
Broad Values -> Describe what broad values are explicitly or implicitly expressed by the vision. <u>Broad values</u> : general moral guiding principles and life goals (e.g. justice, responsibility, harmony with nature) informed by people's worldviews and embedded in a society's institutions. They are the general background of specific values of nature (IPBES SPM; Diaz et al. 2015). <i>This category is broadly linked to 'Views' from Chapter 1.</i>	
Specific Values of Nature -> Describe what specific values of nature are explicitly or implicitly expressed by the vision. <u>Instrumental values</u> : associated with entities as means to achieve or satisfy human ends. Nature is seen as a resource which is important insofar as it provides subsistence. For instance, references to economic development and monetary benefits. The instrumental consideration enables abstraction or generalization from the specific context and from the unrepeatable characteristics of the relationships with nature (Anderson et al., 2022; Arias-Arévalo et al., 2017; Himes and Muraca, 2018). <u>Intrinsic values</u> : Associated with entities worth protecting as ends in-and-of themselves. The value is regardless of the importance or usefulness to people. Not substitutable (Anderson et al., 2022; Himes and Muraca, 2018). <u>Relational values</u> : Based on meaningful and often reciprocal people-nature relations and people-people through	

<p>nature. The relationship itself matters more than means to an end. They include the value of nature for good life. Topics highly linked to relational values: identity, cultural heritage, subsistence/livelihood, embeddedness, self-transformation, spirituality, sacred values, conviviality. They are non-substitutable and highly personal (Anderson et al., 2022; Arias-Arévalo et al., 2018; Chan et al., 2018; Deplazes-Zemp and Chapman, 2021; Himes and Muraca, 2018; Neuteleers, 2020).</p>	
<p>Direct Drivers -> Describe what direct drivers are included in the vision and how they are addressed. <u>Direct drivers:</u> Drivers, both non human-induced and anthropogenic, that affect nature directly. Direct anthropogenic drivers are those that flow from indirect drivers (IPBES, 2019). They include: land-use change, sea use, climate change, pollution, natural resource use and exploitation, invasive species (as per coding spreadsheet). <i>This category is broadly linked to 'actions' and 'power' items from Chapter 1.</i></p>	
<p>Indirect Drivers (Actions, structures, power shifts) -> Describe what indirect drivers are included in the vision and how they are addressed. <u>Indirect drivers:</u> Human actions and decisions that affect nature diffusely by altering and influencing direct drivers as well as other indirect drivers. They do not physically impact nature or its contributions to people (IPBES, 2019). They include demographic, technological, economic and governance (as per coding spreadsheet). While values are indirect drivers, we don't consider them here as they have separate categories. <i>This category is broadly linked to 'actions', 'structures' and 'power' items from Chapter 1.</i></p>	
<p>Open coding -> Please put here relevant information that cannot be included elsewhere.</p>	

References

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